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Enchodelus georgiensis sp. nov. (Nematoda, Dorylaimida) from
Eastern Georgia

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ABSTRACT. Soil nematodes of Gombory ridge and Algethi reserve (Eastern Georgia) have been studied. We found dorylaimid nematodes described as a new species *Enchodelus georgiensis*. © 2006 Bull. Georg. Natl. Acad. Sci.

Key words: odontostyle, odontophore, spicule, supplement.

The details of description of a new species of nematode from range Dorylaimida is given in the article.

Enchodelus georgiensis sp. nov. Measurements:

Females(2): L=0.88-1.10; a=12.7-16.0; b=4.1-5.0; c=35-45; v=44.0-45.8 %; Odontostyle-27.5mkm; Odontophore-35.3-36.3mkm.

Males (2): L=1.0-1.3mm; a=16-22; b=4.2-5.0; c=42-44;

Spic.44.0-44.2mkm; suppl.-11; Odontostyle 27.5mkm; Odontophore-35.8-36.5m; (Gombori population).

Female (1): L=1.0mm; a=16.5; b=5.0; c=47; v=44 %; Odontostyle – 28.6mkm; Odontophore – 36.3mkm.

Males (2): L=1.0-1.2mm; a=21; b=4.9-5.1; c=47; spic.-38.5-40.7mkm; suppl.9-11; Odontostyle-28.6mkm; Odontophore -36.3mkm.(Algethi population).

Holotype: ♀ L=1.1mm; a=16; b=5.0; c=43; v=45.8 %; Odontostyle-27.5mkm; Odontophore-36.3mkm.

Allotype: ♂ L=1.0mm; a=16; b=5.0; c=42; Odontostyle-27.5mkm; Odontophore- 35.8 mkm; spic.-35.8; suppl. - 11.

Body thick, cylindrical, weakly narrowed by both extremities. Cuticle with prominent longitudinal lines. The width of cuticle by level of odontostyle equal to 3.3mkm, but by tail – 7.7mkm. Labial region distinctly separated from body contour; its width about 12mkm. Odontostyle narrow, awl shaped, its length 27.5-28.6mkm, orifice very little, only 1/12 of its length. Odontophore with clear flanges, its length 35.3-36.5mkm. The guiding ring situated by the middle of odontostyle. Amphids goblet shaped, width more than head diameter. The oesophagus enlarged to the middle.

Reproductive system amphidelphic, reflexed. Vulva preequatorial, vagina weakly sclerotized. The size of eggs 62.2 x 40-47.6mkm. Prerectum 2.5 times longer than rectum.

Length of spicules more than tail. Supplements 9-11. The shape of tail convex-conoid to hemispherical, short, less than anal body diameter [Figure].

Differential diagnosis: The new species *Enchodelus georgiensis* belongs to group of species with convex-conoid or hemispherical tail resembling to *Enchodelus altherri* [1], but differs by some distinguished features: the body some shorter and stout; labial region clear set off; amphids more wide; vulva preequatorial; the number of supplements more than *E. altherri*; tail shorter.

Habitat: Gombory mountain ridge, „Mere”, *Carpineta mixtofruticosa*, moss and *Algethi* reserve, firry forest, soil.

The material is kept at the laboratory of soil zoology of the Institute of Zoology.

Key to species of *Enchodelus* with convex-conoid to hemispherical tail [2]

1/6. Odontostyle very short, its width equal labial diameter.

2/3. Odontophore 1.5-1.7 times more than odontostyle ----- *E. laevis*

3/2. Odontophore almost equal odontostyle or slightly more.

4/5. Body length under 1 mm; males unknown ----- *E. parvus*

5/4. Body length more than 1.5 mm; males known; suppl=15-18 -----

----- *E. brasiliensis*

6/1. Odontostyle short or long, but every time more than labial diameter.

7/8. Body length noticeably more than 2 mm; ----- *E. groenlandicus*

8/7. Body length under 2 mm;

9/27. Odontophore more than odontostyle, (about 1.3-1.5 times)

10/11. Labial region low, lips don't set off from body contour -----

----- *E. vesuviarius*

11/12. Labial region not low, more or less set off from body contour.

12/13. Odontostyle very small, its length 12 mkm -----

----- *E. knuppenburgensis*

13/12. Odontostyle noticeably longer.

14/15. Tail tongue shaped, its length equal anal diameter or more -----

----- *E. irregularis*

15/14. Tail hemispherical or convex conoid, not tongue shaped.

16/25. Odontostyle 2 times more than labial diameter.

17/20. Odontostyle length 30 mkm or more.

18/19. Odontostyle length 30-34 mkm; odontophore without flanges -----

----- *E. analatus*

19/18. Odontostyle length 36 mkm; odontophores with flanges -----

----- *E. distinctus*

20/17. Odontostyle length under 30 mkm; males known.

21/24. Odontostyle length 25-29mkm.

22/23. Labial region weakly set off from body contour. Length of spicule =50-55mkm --

----- *E. alterry*

23/22. Labial region well set off from body contour. Length of spicule = 38.5-44.2mkm

----- *E. georgiensis*

24/21. Odontostyle length 20-23 mkm; labial region well set off from body contour ----

----- *E. hoppedorus*

25/16. Odontostyle less than 2 times more labial diameter

26/27. Tail very short, obvious less than anal diameter, hemispherical -----

----- *E. lucinensis*

27/26. Tail convex- conoid, not very short, its length not less than anal diameter.

28/29. Oesofagus enlarged in the middle; index "c"=69 -----

----- *E. vestibulifer*

29/28. Oesofagus enlarged at the 60% its length; index „c"= 50 -----

----- *E. teres*

30/9. There are no marked difference in the length of odontostyle and odontophore.

31/34. The length of odontostyle and odontophore equal or odontophore slightly more than odontostyle.

32/33. The length of odontostyle and odontophore almost equal. Odontostyle 2 times more than labial diameter. Males known ----- *E. arcticus*

A – Anterior region; B – Female head; C – Female tail; D – Vulva region; E – Spicules and supplements

33/32. Odontostyle slightly less than odontophore; odontostyle length 1.5 times more than labial diameter. Males unknown ----- *E. hopedoroides*

34/31. Odontostyle noticeably less than odontophore.

35/36. Labial region low and obtuse; odontophore with flanges; suppl. = 6-13; -----

----- *E. macrodorus*

36/35. Labial region not low, well set off from body contour, odontophore flanges weak or not developed.

37/38. Odontostyle length 40-42mkm; males known -----

----- *E. microdorooides*

38/37. Odontostyle length 21-22mkm; males unknown -----

----- *E. parateres*

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აღმოსავლეთ საქართველოდან

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